

INTERMEDIATE QUANTIFIERS AND THE PROBLEMS OF NON-MONOTONIC LOGIC

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1 Introduction

In the previous publications, we focused on a formal theory of intermediate quantifiers e.g. “Most”, “Several”, “Almost all”, etc., and non-trivial syllogisms with them (see [6]) that are part of *fuzzy natural logic* (FNL). In this paper we will show that our theory is also capable of solving problems of non-monotonic logic (cf. [2]).

Non-monotonicity is the following feature of commonsense reasoning: we formulate a theory determined by axioms that are “normally true”. However, a new formula(s) may occur that we apparently consider to be true as well but which leads to a conclusion contradicting the original theory. We want to update the original theory to contain both the original conclusions as well as the new ones. The latter, however, contradict the original ones. What should we do?

A typical example of nonmonotonic reasoning is the classical *bird-penguin problem*. We start with the commonsense knowledge “All birds can fly”. A new information tells us that “Some birds are penguins” and we know that “No penguins can fly”. Joining the latter with the former leads in classical logic to a contradiction.

We argue that “All” in commonsense reasoning, in fact, means “Most” or “Almost all”. Classical logic suggests no convincing solution how to express it. In this paper we prove that replacing the classical quantifier \forall by a vague intermediate quantifier *Most* the above problem disappears. Hence, if we modify the original default knowledge into $(Most\ x)(Bird\ x, CanFly\ x)$ (“*most* birds can fly”) then we can prove formally in FNL that the additional information saying that “Penguins are birds which cannot fly” does not lead to a contradiction and so, the resulting theory is consistent. The reason consists in the vagueness of linguistic expressions used in common-sense reasoning and their appropriate mathematical model within FNL. We will show that also non-trivial intermediate syllogisms allow consistent revision by a new information. Note that nonmonotonic reasoning is related to the properties of sub/contrary in the graded square of opposition analyzed in [5].

2 Preliminaries

The theory of intermediate quantifiers is a special formal theory T^{IQ} in fuzzy type theory (FTT), see [7].

An intermediate quantifier of type $\langle 1, 1 \rangle$ is one of the following formulas:

$$(Q_{Ev}^{\forall} x)(B, A) \equiv (\exists z)[(\forall x)((B|z)x \Rightarrow Ax) \wedge Ev((\mu B)(B|z))], \quad (1)$$

$$(Q_{Ev}^{\exists} x)(B, A) \equiv (\exists z)[(\exists x)((B|z)x \wedge Ax) \wedge Ev((\mu B)(B|z))]. \quad (2)$$

where Ev is an evaluative linguistic expression (see [8] and Figure 1), μ is a measure on fuzzy sets and $B|z$ is an operation of a *cut* of a fuzzy set B using z .

In this paper, we will consider some (arbitrary) model \mathcal{M} of T^{IQ} and a selected universe M . We will use special notation for the interpretation of the formula $Ev(\mu(B)(B|z))$, namely, if \mathcal{M} is a model and $B, Z \subseteq M$ are fuzzy sets then

$$F_{Ev}^R(B, B|Z) = \mathcal{M}(Ev(\mu(B)(B|z))).$$

where the cut $B|Z$ is a fuzzy subset of B consisting of all singletons a/x , $x \in M$ that are equal to the corresponding singletons of Z .

A semantic interpretation of intermediate quantifiers (1) and (2) are truth values given by the respective formulas

$$Q_{Ev}^{\forall}(B, A) = \bigvee \left\{ \bigwedge_{u \in N} ((B|Z)(u) \rightarrow A(u)) \wedge F_{Ev}^R(B, B|Z) \mid Z \in \mathcal{F}(N) \right\}, \quad (3)$$

$$Q_{Ev}^{\exists}(B, A) = \bigvee \left\{ \bigvee_{u \in N} ((B|Z)(u) \wedge A(u)) \wedge F_{Ev}^R(B, B|Z) \mid Z \in \mathcal{F}(N) \right\}. \quad (4)$$

Figure 1: Extensions of evaluative expressions $Sm \bar{v}$, $\neg Sm \bar{v}$ and $Bi Ex$ in the context $[0, 0.4] \cup [0.4, 1]$ with marked interpretation of points $\mathbf{a}_{\neg Sm \bar{v}}$, $\mathbf{a}_{Bi Ex}$ and $\neg \mathbf{c}_{Sm \bar{v}}$.

In this paper, we will consider the following intermediate quantifiers:

$$\mathbf{A:} \text{ All } B \text{ are } A := (Q_{Bi\Delta}^{\forall} x)(B, A) \equiv (\forall x)(Bx \Rightarrow Ax),$$

$$\mathbf{E:} \text{ No } B \text{ are } A := (Q_{Bi\Delta}^{\forall} x)(B, \neg A) \equiv (\forall x)(Bx \Rightarrow \neg Ax),$$

$$\mathbf{P:} \text{ Almost all } B \text{ are } A := (Q_{BiE_x}^{\forall} x)(B, A)$$

$$\mathbf{B:} \text{ Almost all } B \text{ are not } A := (Q_{BiE_x}^{\forall} x)(B, \neg A)$$

$$\mathbf{T:} \text{ Most } B \text{ are } A := (Q_{BiV_e}^{\forall} x)(B, A)$$

$$\mathbf{D:} \text{ Most } B \text{ are not } A := (Q_{BiV_e}^{\forall} x)(B, \neg A)$$

$$\mathbf{K:} \text{ Many } B \text{ are } A := (Q_{\neg Sm}^{\forall} x)(B, A)$$

$$\mathbf{G:} \text{ Many } B \text{ are not } A := (Q_{\neg Sm}^{\forall} x)(B, \neg A)$$

$$\mathbf{I:} \text{ Some } B \text{ are } A := (Q_{Bi\Delta}^{\exists} x)(B, A) \equiv (\exists x)(Bx \wedge Ax),$$

$$\mathbf{O:} \text{ Some } B \text{ are not } A := (Q_{Bi\Delta}^{\exists} x)(B, \neg A) \equiv (\exists x)(Bx \wedge \neg Ax)$$

where Δ is the Baaz delta keeping the membership degree 1 and sending all lower membership degrees to 0.

3 Nonmonotonicity and intermediate quantifiers

3.1 Bird-penguin problem

We start with a commonsense knowledge

- (i) $(\text{All } x)(\text{Bird } x, \text{CanFly } x)$ (“all birds can fly”).
- (ii) $(\text{Some } x)(\text{Bird } x, \text{Penguin } x)$ (“some birds are penguins”).
- (iii) $(\forall x)(\text{Penguin } x \Rightarrow \neg \text{CanFly } x)$ (“no penguins can fly”).

Axiom (ii) is a new information causing that such a theory is contradictory.

However, we can modify the original default knowledge (i) by

- (i') $(\text{Most } x)(\text{Bird } x, \text{CanFly } x)$ (“most birds can fly”)

which is a natural modification since we know that most birds fly but not all. Then we can prove that the new theory is consistent.

Theorem 1 *Let us consider an extension T of the theory of intermediate quantifiers T^{IQ} and $\text{Bird}, \text{Penguin}, \text{CanFly} \in \text{Form}_{\alpha}$ be formulas. Let*

$$T \vdash (\text{Most } x_{\alpha})(\text{Bird } x, \text{CanFly } x), \tag{5}$$

$$T \vdash (\exists x_{\alpha})\Delta(\text{Bird } x \wedge \text{Penguin } x), \tag{6}$$

$$T \vdash (\forall x_{\alpha})(\text{Penguin } x \Rightarrow \neg \text{CanFly } x). \tag{7}$$

Then $T \vdash (\exists x_{\alpha})(\text{Bird } x \wedge \neg \text{CanFly } x)$ and T is consistent.

Hence, we proved formally in our theory that additional information saying that “Penguins are birds which cannot fly” does lead to a contradiction. The reason consists in the vagueness of expressions of natural language that are used in commonsense reasoning. In our case, we replace the precise quantifier \forall by a vague intermediate quantifier *Most* which allows exceptions and so, the above nonmonotonicity problem disappears.

3.2 Default rules

The reasoning above is related to default logic. The defaults are represented as inference rules rather than object language formulas. Reiter in [9] argues that defaults cannot be reasoned about within the logic. For example, he discusses the following example from [3]: “Normally canaries are yellow” and “Yellow things are never green” and he argues that we cannot conclude “Normally canaries are never green”. McDermott and Doyle’s suggestion is to have the following sequence of inferences:

- $(\forall x)(\text{CANARY}(x) \& M \text{YELLOW}(x) \Rightarrow \neg \text{YELLOW}(x))$,
- $(\forall x)(\text{YELLOW}(x) \Rightarrow \neg \text{GREEN}(x))$,
- we can infer that $(\forall x)(\text{CANARY}(x) \& M \text{YELLOW}(x) \Rightarrow \neg \text{GREEN}(x))$

where MA is intended to mean “ A is consistent”. Reiter in [9] casts doubts, whether the last formula can legitimately be interpreted to mean “Normally canaries are not green”.

We argue that in our theory of intermediate quantifiers and syllogisms this is possible, has a good sense and does not lead to a contradiction. Indeed, what does it mean

$$\text{“Normally } Ax \text{ are } Bx\text{”?} \tag{8}$$

This sentence immediately suggests that there can be abnormal situations in which Ax are not Bx . But only exceptionally and otherwise we expect Ax followed by Bx to happen in *most* cases. Hence, we naturally understand sentence (8) either as “Most Ax are Bx ”, or “Almost all Ax are Bx ”, but *not* as “All Ax are Bx ”.

A short analysis reveals that the previous example can be modeled in our theory as follows:

$$\begin{array}{l} \mathbf{E}: (\forall x)(\text{Yellow } x \Rightarrow \neg \text{Green } x), \\ \mathbf{T}: (\text{Most } x)(\text{Canary } x, \text{Yellow } x), \\ \hline \mathbf{D}: (\text{Most } x)(\text{Canary } x, \neg \text{Green } x). \end{array}$$

This is a *special case* of the *valid syllogism* **ETD-I** of the first figure. Its validity was proved in [4].

3.3 Sorites/falakros paradoxes

We argue that the classical sorites/falakros paradoxes are also cases of nonmonotonic reasoning. The following is a solution of the paradoxes using intermediate quantifier “Not many”.

Theorem 2 *Let $\sigma = o(o\epsilon)$ be a type for natural numbers in fuzzy type theory (cf. [1, Chapter 6]) and T be a consistent extension of the theory of intermediate quantifiers T^{IQ} that contains Peano arithmetics. Let $0, n, m_0 \in Form_\sigma$ represent natural numbers and $\mathbb{FN} \in Form_{o\sigma}$. If the following formulas are provable*

$$T \vdash \mathbb{FN} 0, \quad (9)$$

$$T \vdash (\text{Not many } n)((\mathbb{FN} n), (\mathbb{FN}(n+1) \vee (n \equiv m_0))), \quad (10)$$

$$T \vdash (\exists n)\neg(\mathbb{FN} n). \quad (11)$$

then T is consistent.

It is interesting in the proof of this theorem that we may consider \mathbb{FN} to be a *finite set* of natural numbers, i.e., a set which contains all numbers n saying, that, e.g., a person having n hairs is bald. Moreover, the implication

$$(\mathbb{FN} n) \Rightarrow (\mathbb{FN}(n+1) \vee (n \equiv m_0))$$

is true for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$. The number m_0 is a number of, e.g., hairs on one’s head for which we know that he/she is *not bald*. This is the number assured by axiom (11).

Interpretation of formula (10) can be rewritten as

$$\bigvee_{Z \subseteq \mathbb{FN}} \left(\bigwedge_{n \in \mathbb{N}} ((\mathbb{FN} | Z)(n) \rightarrow \mathbb{FN}(n+1) \vee [n \equiv m_0]) \wedge F_{S_m \bar{\nu}}^R(\mathbb{FN}, \mathbb{FN} | Z) \right) \quad (12)$$

where $[n \equiv m_0] \in \{0, 1\}$ is a truth value of the equality $n = m_0$.

We can see from (12) that the quantifier “Not many” contains the value

$$F_{S_m \bar{\nu}}^R(\mathbb{FN}, \mathbb{FN} | Z) \in [0, 1]$$

which accompanies each step n . If the number of steps is too large, i.e., $|\mathbb{FN}| \geq m_0$, then $F_{S_m \bar{\nu}}^R(\mathbb{FN}, \mathbb{FN} | Z) = 0$. This value can be taken as a characterization of how much dubious is the implication $\mathbb{FN}(n) \Rightarrow \mathbb{FN}(n+1)$. Namely, $F_{S_m \bar{\nu}}^R(\mathbb{FN}, \mathbb{FN} | Z) = 1$ means that the latter implication is not dubious at all and $F_{S_m \bar{\nu}}^R(\mathbb{FN}, \mathbb{FN} | Z) = 0$ means, that it is completely dubious.

4 Conclusion

In this paper we pointed out some known problems of nonmonotonic logic and demonstrated that they can be overcome in the theory of intermediate quantifiers. Namely, it follows from vagueness of their semantics that existence of exceptions to default rules does not lead to contradiction and we need no special modification of the formal fuzzy logic. We also demonstrated that the classical sorites/falakros paradoxes are also examples of nonmonotonic reasoning.

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